

LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT SIMULATION WITH A SPECIAL FOCUS ON THICK COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Test and simulation of low velocity impact on composite structures is often limited to thin laminates. Several applications in the aerospace and automotive industry exist, e.g. high-lift devices and high-pressure vessels, with laminate thicknesses of several centimetres. This paper investigates the influence of laminate thickness on damage initiation and propagation during low velocity impact. An enhanced cohesive zone model is presented, which accounts for i) internal friction, ii) crack surface enlargement due to through-the-thickness compression, iii) strain rate effects and iv) different damage initiation stresses in the traction separation law of undamaged and damage delamination layers. The effect of each feature is discussed and the model is validated on 2mm to 12mm thick laminates. The numerical results closely match the test results and significant improvements compared to conventional cohesive zone models can be found for the initiation and propagation of delamination.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays fiber-reinforced composite structures are widely used in the aerospace industry; however, it still remains a challenge to predict the complex damage mechanisms during the development phase. Of particular concern is low-velocity impact damage that can result in significant internal delamination and residual strength reduction. Following a “no-growth” certification strategy according to AMC 20-29, current design procedures limit the allowable stresses and strains in the laminate, so that barely visible impact damage (BVID) does not grow at ultimate load. Consequently, conservative design allowables limit the potential weight reduction associated with composite materials and extensive test programs must be performed. [1,2]

The simulation of impact and residual strength after impact has been widely studied. Modelling approaches range from analytical [3–5], layered shell [6], stacked shell [7–9], stacked continuum shell [10], stacked solid [9,11,12] and discrete damage [13–15] models. “Stacked” models can be considered as state-of-the-art. This approach typically represents each ply, or sub-set of plies, with one layer of elements having a fracture mode dependent, anisotropic failure criteria for damage initiation and a continuum damage mechanics model for damage propagation. The interfaces between plies can be connected with cohesive surfaces, cohesive contact or cohesive zone elements to model delamination. While discrete damage models are able to capture damage progression more realistically, the stacked shell approach does offer a good compromise between accuracy and numerical efficiency [9,16].

Most publications focus on the simulation of impact on laminates with a thickness of 2-5mm. While undoubtedly most structures are made of thin laminates, certain aerospace and automotive applications do have laminate thicknesses of several centimeters [17–19]. This paper investigates the influence of laminate thickness on the low-velocity impact response of composite structures. Shortcomings of current material models are identified and an enhanced cohesive zone model formulation is presented.

2 MATERIALS & TEST SET-UP

2.1 Materials

All test specimens investigated in this study have been manufactured from carbon fiber biaxial non-crimp fabric (TENAX-E HTS40 F13 12K [20]) with an area weight of 557 g/m² and one part epoxy resin (RTM 6 [21]) using vacuum assisted processing at Airbus CRT. A thermoplastic binder fleece PA-1541 (manufacturer: Spunfab Ltd) was placed between each fabric layer and the layup was pre-compacted under vacuum at 120°C for 60min to achieve the desired ply thickness of 0.25mm. The preheated resin is infused at 100°C and cured at 180°C for 2h. In total, three different laminate thicknesses (2mm, 6mm, 12mm) with a quasi-isotropic layup were manufactured for testing. Table 1 summarizes the material properties. Some parameters were not characterized and had to be adapted based on available data from similar materials. These parameters are underlined in Table 1.

Intralaminar Stiffness		Intralaminar Strength		Intralaminar Fracture Toughness		Interlaminar Properties	
E_{1t} [GPa]	140	R_{1t} [MPa]	2160	G_{1t} [N/mm]	<u>120</u>	E_3 [GPa]	8.6
E_{1c} [GPa]	126	R_{1c} [MPa]	1236	G_{1c} [N/mm]	<u>30</u>	G_{13} [GPa]	4.2
E_2 [GPa]	8.6	R_2 [MPa]	67	G_{2t} [N/mm]	0.385	R_{33}^{ini} [MPa]	50.6
G_{12} [GPa]	4.2	R_{12} [MPa]	70	G_{2c} [N/mm]	<u>1.5</u>	R_{33}^{pr} [MPa]	25.3
ϑ_{12} [-]	0.3	α [-]	1			R_{13}^{ini} [MPa]	58.3
						R_{13}^{pr} [MPa]	29.2
						G_I [N/mm]	0.385
						G_{II} [N/mm]	1.19
						η [-]	2.58

Table 1: Material properties of TENAX-E HTS40 F13 12K / RTM 6 (partially taken from [22]) (underlined parameters were adapted from similar materials)

2.2 Test set-up

Impact tests are performed according to the Airbus test standard AITM1-0010. Figure 1 shows the test set-up. Additionally, static impact tests are performed with a constant crosshead displacement of 2mm/min to enable a comparison of rate effect on damage initiation and propagation.

After impact, the delamination is characterized by non-destructive testing (NDT) using an Omniscan MX-2 phased-array ultrasonic device with a 5L64-NW1 probe head. The device generates an elastic wave inside the composite plate through piezo-elements, which is strongly reflected either at the specimen back-face or at a delaminated interface. By measuring the time between sending and receiving the elastic wave and calibrating the elastic wave speed inside the composite plate with an undamaged test specimen, the depth of the reflecting interface can be determined. Figure 1 b) exemplarily shows a B-, D- and C-scan of an impacted composite plate. B- and D-scans represent a cut along the specimen width and height. They depict the intensity of the reflected signal (red represents high intensity) with respect to the distance to the probe head. Finally, the C-scan plots the depth corresponding to the highest reflection over the specimen surface and can be used to visualize delamination. Due to the severe reflection at delamination interfaces, no information is available about the state of delamination further away from the probe head.

Figure 1: Test set-up of impact test (left: (1) specimen, (2) fixture, (3) impactor) and evaluation of delamination by phased array ultrasonic testing (right)

3 MODEL DESCRIPTION

During impact fiber and matrix failure as well as delamination occur in the composite plates. In order to capture the complex damage mechanisms the composite laminate is modelled using a stacked-shell approach in which each ply is represented by a dedicated shell layer connected through cohesive zone elements (see Figure 2). An intralaminar and interlaminar damage model is assigned to the shell and cohesive zone elements respectively to model damage initiation and progression.

Figure 2: Simulation model setup

3.1 Intralaminar damage model

The ABAQUS anisotropic damage and failure model for fiber-reinforced composites [23] is used to model intralaminar damage. This applies Hashin's theory for damage initiation, which expresses the failure surface in effective stress space and considers four different damage initiation mechanisms as summarized in Table 2.

	Fiber	Matrix
tension	$F_f^t = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{R_{1t}}\right)^2 + \alpha \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{R_{12}}\right)^2$	$F_m^t = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{R_{2t}}\right)^2 + \alpha \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{R_{12}}\right)^2$
compression	$F_f^c = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{R_{1c}}\right)^2$	$F_m^c = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2R_{12}}\right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{R_{2c}}{2R_{12}}\right)^2 - 1\right] \frac{\sigma_{22}}{R_{2c}} + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{R_{12}}\right)^2$

Table 2: Hashin failure criteria

The response of the damaged material is computed according to [24,25] as

$$\sigma = C_d \cdot \varepsilon \quad , \quad (1)$$

with

$$C_d = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)E_1 & (1-d_f)(1-d_m)v_{21}E_1 & 0 \\ (1-d_f)(1-d_m)v_{12}E_2 & (1-d_m)E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-d_s)G_{12} \cdot D \end{bmatrix} \quad , \quad (2)$$

$$D = 1 - (1-d_f)(1-d_m)v_{12}v_{21} \quad , \quad (3)$$

where C_d is the damaged elasticity matrix, E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} , v_{12} and v_{21} are the longitudinal and transverse elastic modulus and shear modulus as well as Poisson's ratio and σ and ε are vectors of stress and strain. The fiber and matrix damage variables for compression and tension d_f^t , d_f^c , d_m^t and d_m^c , as well as shear d_s are further defined as follows:

$$d_f = \begin{cases} d_f^t & \text{for } \sigma_{11} \geq 0 \\ d_f^c & \text{for } \sigma_{11} \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad , \quad (3)$$

$$d_m = \begin{cases} d_m^t & \text{for } \sigma_{22} \geq 0 \\ d_m^c & \text{for } \sigma_{22} \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad , \quad (4)$$

$$d_s = 1 - (1-d_f^t)(1-d_f^c)(1-d_m^t)(1-d_m^c) \quad . \quad (5)$$

The evolution of damage is based on the crack band model [26] and is governed by the fracture toughness associated to the four damage modes $G_{C,Mode}$. To alleviate mesh dependency a characteristic length, defined as the square root of the element surface, is introduced so that the constitutive law can be expressed as a stress-displacement relationship. Assuming a linear degradation, as shown in Figure 3, the damage variable can be computed as

$$d_{Mode} = \frac{\delta_{eq,Mode}^f (\delta_{eq,Mode} - \delta_{eq,Mode}^0)}{\delta_{eq,Mode} (\delta_{eq,Mode}^f - \delta_{eq,Mode}^0)} \quad , \quad (6)$$

with

$$\delta_{eq,Mode}^f = \frac{2 \cdot G_{C,Mode}}{\sigma_{eq,Mode}^0} \quad (7)$$

where the subscript *Mode* refers to the individual damage mode and corresponding equivalent displacement. Further information concerning this intralaminar damage model are given in reference [23].

Figure 3: Traction-separation law for intralaminar damage model (a) and mixed mode traction-separation law for cohesive zone model (b)

3.2 Interlaminar damage model

A user-defined material model for finite thickness cohesive zone elements is developed and implemented in ABAQUS for explicit time integration (VUMAT [23]) to model the pressure- and strain rate dependent interlaminar damage initiation and propagation.

Basic cohesive zone element formulation

The cohesive zone model relates traction t to relative displacement δ of two interfaces. For further evaluation the opening model (Mode I) and resultant shear mode (Mode II) are considered, so that the corresponding displacement for pure mode (δ_I, δ_{II}) and mixed-mode (δ_m) loading can be computed as:

$$\delta_I = \langle \delta_{33} \rangle , \quad (8)$$

$$\delta_{II} = \sqrt{\delta_{13}^2 + \delta_{23}^2} , \quad (9)$$

$$\delta_m = \sqrt{\delta_I^2 + \delta_{II}^2} , \quad (10)$$

where δ_{33} is the out-of-plane displacement, δ_{13} and δ_{23} are the in-plane displacements and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is the Macauley bracket, i.e. $\langle \cdot \rangle = \max(\cdot, 0)$. From the interface stiffness K_I and K_{II} for Mode I and Mode II loading, the traction components can be calculated as:

$$t_I = \begin{cases} (1 - d_{cze})K_I \delta_I & \text{for } \delta_I \geq 0 \\ K_I \delta_I & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} , \quad (11)$$

$$t_{II} = (1 - d_{cze})K_{II} \delta_{II} , \quad (12)$$

with the static damage variable d_{cze} . In the basic model a bi-linear traction-separation law is adopted, which is typically used to model delamination. For damage initiation a quadratic stress-based criterion is used:

$$\left(\frac{\langle t_I \rangle}{t_I^0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_{II}}{t_{II}^0} \right)^2 = 1 . \quad (13)$$

The area below the traction-separation curve is equivalent to the material fracture toughness. For mixed mode loading, the fracture toughness is calculated by the B-K-Model [27]:

$$G_c = G_{Ic} + (G_{IIc} - G_{Ic}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} \right)^\eta , \quad (14)$$

where G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} are the experimentally characterized fracture toughness in Mode I and Mode II, η is the B-K-Parameter fitted to test data for mixed-mode loading and G_I and G_{II} are the instantaneous strain energy release rates calculated by numerical integration of the individual traction-separation laws for Mode I and Mode II during loading. Finally, the static damage variable for the time step T is given by

$$d_{cze}^T = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{t_m^0 (\delta_m^f - \delta_m^t)}{(\delta_m^f - \delta_m^0) ((K_I \delta_I)^2 + (K_{II} \delta_{II})^2)^{0.5}} & \text{for } \delta_m > \delta_m^0 \text{ and } \delta_m^T > \delta_m^{T-1} \\ d_{cze}^{T-1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} , \quad (15)$$

with

$$\delta_m^f = \frac{2G_c}{t_m^0} , \quad (16)$$

Friction model

Experimental observations have shown that through-the-thickness compressive loading can influence damage initiation and damage propagation. Puck [28] relates this to an internal friction coefficient, which results in an increased shear strength for inter-fiber failure Mode B. Furthermore, it is assumed that after damage initiation, the friction forces act on the fracture surface contribute to energy dissipation and that the internal and interlaminar friction coefficients are similar. As shown in Figure 4, the resulting traction-separation law is then scaled, keeping the degradation slope constant. The resulting mode II damage initiation $t_{II,fr}^0$ and fracture toughness $G_{IIc,fr}$ can be calculated as follows:

$$f_{fr} = \begin{cases} \frac{t_{II}^0 - \mu_{fr} t_I}{t_{II}^0}, & \text{for } t_I < 0 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (16)$$

$$t_{II,fr}^0 = t_{II}^0 \cdot f_{fr}, \quad (17)$$

$$G_{IIc,fr} = G_{IIc} \cdot f_{fr}^2, \quad (18)$$

with the friction scaling factor f_{fr} . The friction coefficient μ_{fr} can either be characterized through friction testing [29], or computed from Pucks failure envelope [30]. In this study a typical value of $\mu_{fr} = 0.27$ has been chosen.

Figure 4: Friction model, crack length model and strain rate model for cohesive zone elements

Crack length model

In addition to friction effects, it has been observed that compressive loading increases the fracture angle at the interface [31] and therefore effectively increases the fracture surface as shown in Figure 4.

Since this three-dimensional crack growth cannot be modelled micromechanically with a single layer of cohesive zone elements between each ply, it must be included in the mode II fracture toughness. Therefore, a fracture-plane-based model is developed. From the local stress state in the cohesive zone element, the angle to the principle stress is calculated according to Mohr's circle:

$$\theta_{mohr} = \frac{1}{2} \arctan\left(-\frac{2t_{II}}{t_I}\right) . \quad (19)$$

The local fracture angle is assumed to be tangential to the principle stress plane [32]:

$$\theta_{fp} = \frac{\pi}{2} + \theta_{mohr} . \quad (20)$$

Next, the fracture surface is considered to have a saw tooth shape [31], a fictitious thickness d_{if} and length l_{if} as well as a crack inclination of θ_{fp} (see Figure 4). Given a constant depth w_{if} , the crack surface is given by:

$$A_{\theta_{fp}} = \left(\frac{d_{if}}{\sin(\pi - \theta_{fp})} + d_{if} \right) \frac{l_{if} \tan(\pi - \theta_{fp})}{d_{if}} . \quad (20)$$

The increase in fracture toughness with respect to the mode II fracture toughness associated with a fracture angle of 135° is equivalent to the increase of the crack surface:

$$\begin{aligned} f_{cl} = \frac{G_{IIc,cl}}{G_{IIc}} = \frac{A_{\theta_{fp}}}{A_{135^\circ}} &= \frac{\left(\frac{d_{if}}{\sin(\pi - \theta_{fp})} + d_{if} \right) \frac{l_{if} \tan(\pi - \theta_{fp})}{d_{if}}}{\left(\frac{d_{if}}{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)} + d_{if} \right) \frac{l_{if} \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)}{d_{if}}} \\ &= \frac{\tan(\pi - \theta_{fp}) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sin(\pi - \theta_{fp})} \right)}{1 + \frac{1}{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)}} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Since the effect of compressive loading on damage initiation is already included in the *friction model*, damage initiation must remain unaffected by the crack length model. Investigations have shown that a specimen under compressive loading will experience a significantly higher plastic shear deformation and failure strain [30]. The increase in fracture toughness associated to the crack length model

$$\Delta G_{IIc,cl} = (f_{cl} - 1)G_{IIc} \quad (22)$$

is therefore introduced to the traction-separation law by adding a section of perfect plasticity followed by linear degradation, with a gradient identical to the initial traction-separation law (see Figure 4). The additional displacement corresponding to the plastic region of the traction-separation law is then given by:

$$\delta_{cl} = \frac{\Delta G_{IIc,cl}}{t_m^0} \quad (23)$$

Strain rate model

For low-velocity impact of thin laminates strain rate dependency is typically neglected; however, for thick laminates the interlaminar shear strain rate increases significantly. To account for this the variation of shear strength is modelled linearly with the logarithm of strain rate [33], so that the increase in shear strength can be calculated as:

$$f_{sr} = \frac{t_{II,sr}^0(\dot{\epsilon})}{t_{II}^0(\dot{\epsilon}_0)} = m_f \log_{10} \frac{\dot{\gamma}}{\dot{\gamma}^0} + 1 = m_f \log_{10} \frac{\delta_{II}}{\delta_{II}^0} + 1 \quad (24)$$

with strain rate $\dot{\gamma}$, quasi-static strain rate $\dot{\gamma}^0$ and the calibration factor m_f . In the absence of strain rate tests for the material investigated in this study, the calibration factor is chose from a similar material (IM7/8552 [34]) characterized quasi-statically ($\dot{\gamma}^0 = 10^{-4} s^{-1}$) and dynamically using a split-Hopkinson bar ($\dot{\gamma} = 350 s^{-1}$). Transverse shear is assumed to behave similar to in-plane shear [35]. An increase in shear strength of approximately 50% was found for IM7/8552. A similar behavior can be observed for other materials of this class [33,35–37].

While inter-fiber failure is clearly influenced by the strain rate, no conclusive results can be found in the literature with respect to fracture toughness [38]. Consequently, a fracture toughness strain rate model is not used in this study.

Delamination layer activation

The transverse tension R_{33}^{ini} and transverse shear R_{13}^{ini} strength are characterized using an undamaged specimen (see Table 1) and are used to predict interlaminar damage initiation. In the cohesive zone model, these strengths correspond to t_I^0 and t_{II}^0 respectively. However, once the delamination layer is cracked, the traction at damage initiation t_I^0 and t_{II}^0 reduces. The corresponding values R_{33}^{pr} and R_{13}^{pr} , also specified in Table 1, are calibrated to fit Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness tests. Additionally, the strain rate effect is limited to crack initiation, since no effect on fracture toughness is assumed.

The changing parameters for t_I^0 and t_{II}^0 are accounted for in the model using a simple non-local algorithm. Technically, the effect should be limited to those elements within the crack front. However, implementing a crack tip tracking algorithm as described in [39] would be inefficient. It is therefore defined that a delamination layer is cracked once the first integration point in the layer is fully damaged. With the ABAQUS user subroutine VEXTERNALDB, a global array ini_{layer} is initialized to zero for each delamination layer. The first integration to be fully damaged sets the marker to one. Starting from the next time step, each integration within the layer uses the “cracked” parameter set.

Combined model

The combination of the aforementioned models leads to the following corrected mode II damage initiation $t_{II,cor}^0$ and fracture toughness $G_{IIc,cor}$:

$$t_{II,cor}^0 = \begin{cases} R_{13}^{ini}(1 + (f_{fr} - 1)) + (f_{sr} - 1) & \text{for } ini_{layer} = 0 \\ R_{13}^{pr}(1 + (f_{fr} - 1)) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (25)$$

$$G_{IIc,cor} = G_{IIc} \cdot f_{fr} + \Delta G_{IIc,cl}. \quad (26)$$

The static damage variable can now be computed as

$$d_{cze,cor}^T = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{t_m^0(\delta_I^2 + \delta_{II}^2)^{0.5}}{\delta_m^T((K_I \delta_I)^2 + (K_{II} \delta_{II})^2)^{0.5}} & \text{for } \delta_m^0 > \delta_m^T > \delta_m^0 + \delta_{cl} \\ & \text{and } \delta_m^T > \delta_m^{T-1} \\ 1 - \frac{t_m^0(\delta_{m,cor}^f - \delta_m^T)}{(\delta_{m,cor}^f - \delta_m^0)((K_I \delta_I)^2 + (K_{II} \delta_{II})^2)^{0.5}} & \text{for } \delta_m > \delta_m^0 + \delta_{cl} \\ & \text{and } \delta_m^T > \delta_m^{T-1} \\ d_{cze,cor}^{T-1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

with

$$\delta_{m,cor}^f = \frac{2(G_{IIc} \cdot f_{fr})}{t_m^0} + \delta_{cl}. \quad (28)$$

Table 3 summarizes the required parameters for the friction and strain rate model.

μ_{fr}	m_f	$\dot{\gamma}^0$
[-]	[-]	[s ⁻¹]
0.27	0.076	10 ⁻⁴

Table 3: Cohesive zone model parameters for friction model and strain rate model

3.3 Simulation model setup

The simulation model for impact is shown schematically in Figure 2. The impactor, clamps and support table in the impact simulation are modelled as rigid body elements. For the laminate, a stacked shell approach is used with a structured mesh and an element size of 0.45mm. Each ply is represented by fully integrated shell elements to avoid hourglassing and is tied to cohesive zone elements with a thickness of 0.25mm. In order to improve numerical stability, intralaminar damage is limited to 0.998 and no shell elements are deleted to avoid a non-physical loss of mass. Cohesive zone elements, on the other hand, are deleted once fully damaged. Contact modelling is realized through a general contact definition in ABAQUS with an interlaminar friction coefficient of 0.3.

In dynamic impact simulations loads are represented through the impactor mass and velocity as applied in the experiment. In static impact simulation realistic loading rates would result in an unacceptable simulation time, even on a high performance cluster. Consequently, the loading rates are chosen to avoid initial dynamic effects by applying an impactor displacement of 2mm during 0.01s with a smooth step load amplitude and strain rate effects are neglected in the model.

4 EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

First, the effect of the different interlaminar damage models described in section 3.2 shall be demonstrated on the example of a 35J impact on a 12mm thick specimen. The following notation is used:

- (M0) basic cohesive zone element formulation
- (M1) M0 + friction model
- (M2) M1 + crack length model
- (M3) M2 + strain rate model
- (M4) M3 + delamination layer activation
- (M5) M2 + delamination layer activation (“quasi-static model”)

Force-displacement diagrams for these impact studies are presented in Figure 5. In the experiment, a characteristic drop in reaction force can be observed after an almost linear load increase to 22.6kN. This is attributed to first damage initiation. After this drop, the reaction force increases while the specimen compliance decreases indicating delamination propagation. The simulation model that uses the basic cohesive zone element formulation (M0) cannot reproduce the initial force peak, as delamination occurs already at an early stage (4.9 kN). Adding the friction model (M1) and the crack length model (M2) leads, respectively, to increased peak forces of 16.1kN and 18.9kN. To correctly model damage initiation, strain rate effects (M3) must be considered. Combining all the models (M4) the reaction force is closely predicted (22.4kN).

The different interlaminar damage models also significantly influence delamination growth after the initial force peak. Figure 6 compares the experimental and numerical results of the delamination shape and projected delamination size. The damaged cohesive zone elements are therefore plotted with respect to the delamination envelope extracted from the ultrasonic scan. The color refers to the depth of the delamination layer measured from the impacted surface. A stiffening can be observed for the friction, crack length and strain rate model leading to an underestimation of delamination size. The activation of delamination layers significantly improves this. Comparing the delamination shape and size over laminate thickness, the combined model predicts the projected delamination size with an accuracy of 3% and closely captures the delamination shapes.

Figure 5: Experimental and numerical results for 35J impact on 12mm thick laminate: reaction force vs. displacement

Figure 5d) compares the reaction force vs. displacement plot of a static impact test on a 12mm thick laminate with the results of an impact simulation using the combined model but neglecting strain rate effects (M5). Similar to the 35J impact, an initial force peak can be identified in the experiment but at a lower magnitude. Although the basic cohesive zone model is again unable to predict this, it is found that damage initiation is modelled correctly if friction and crack surface enlargement are taken into account, further validating the assumptions made in this enhanced cohesive zone model. Figure 5d) also indicates that no significant strain rate effect on damage propagation exists. After damage initiation, the reaction force vs. displacement curves of the static and dynamic impact are similar. This suggests that fracture toughness is not strain rate dependent.

Differences between simulation and experimental results can be found after delamination occurs. The reaction force drops significantly in the simulation model compared to a more continuous and less severe drop found in the experiment, resulting in a non-negligible increase in dynamic energy. Consequently, results can only be compared up to damage initiation. To further improve results of static simulation a realistic loading rate must be chosen and appropriate structural damping, as well as a softer delamination layer activation algorithm, should be applied.

In order to investigate the effect of the proposed models for different laminate thicknesses, Figure 7 shows the results of the 15J impact on a 2mm thick laminate. Both numerical models (M0, M4) are able to reproduce the reaction force vs. displacement diagram, indicating no significant influence of interlaminar compression and strain rate effects. The delamination size of the advanced cohesive zone model (M4) is larger compared to the basic formulation (M0), which is a result of the delamination layer activation. As shown in Figure 7 part of the backface ply splits and detaches from the laminate in the experiment. The model is unable to capture this behavior, since shell elements are not deleted and retain a residual stiffness. This artificially reinforces the laminate and changes the local interlaminar

loading mode from peeling (experiment) to a shear dominated mixed mode loading causing the local crack driving force to reduce. Discrete damage models as proposed in [14] may be more suited to model this phenomenon.

The results of the 35J impact on a 6mm thick laminate are depicted in Figure 8. Although less prominent compared to the impact studies on 12mm laminates, the effect of through-the-thickness compression and strain rate is evident. The advanced cohesive zone model (M4) is again able to closely predict damage initiation and propagation, as well as delamination size and shape.

Figure 6: Experimental and numerical results for 35J impact on 12mm thick laminate: delamination shape and projected delamination size

Figure 7: Experimental and numerical results for 35J impact in 2mm thick laminate

Figure 8: Experimental and numerical results for 35J impact in 6mm thick laminate

7 CONCLUSIONS

An enhanced cohesive zone model for the simulation of low velocity impact on thick composite plates has been developed and implemented in ABAQUS through a user-defined material model for explicit time integration (VUMAT). In addition to the standard cohesive zone formulation, the model accounts for i) internal friction, ii) crack surface enlargement due to through-the-thickness compression, iii) strain rate effects and iv) different damage initiation stresses in the traction separation law of undamaged and damage delamination layers.

In general, it can be observed that the effect of through-the-thickness compression and strain rate dependency becomes non-negligible with increasing laminate thickness. Through the simulation of quasi-static impact on 12mm thick laminates, the influence of internal friction and crack surface enlargement was investigated. By considering both effects in the model, damage initiation can be closely predicted. Test results of a 35J impact on a 12mm thick laminate reveals additional dynamic effects. Damage initiation increases from 18.2kN in a quasi-static test to 22.6kN in a dynamic impact test. The simulation model correctly predicts this by considering strain rate effects on intralaminar shear strength.

In all cases, it is critical to account for different stresses at damage initiation in the traction separation law for undamaged and damaged laminates. While experimentally characterized transverse tension and shear strength must be used to predict damage initiation, calibrated parameters to fracture mechanics tests must be used for damage propagation. This is introduced to the model through a user-defined model for non-local algorithms (VEXTERNALDB) by changing the corresponding strength in a delamination layer once one integration point is fully damaged. Finally, no strain rate effect of the fracture toughness can be identified from these experiments.

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